

Merocyanines Derived from 3-Methyl Benzo (f) Quinoline

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A number of merocarbo and merodicarbo cyanines derived from 3-methyl benzo(f)quinoline as the fixed basic nucleus and (i) oxazolone, (ii) thiazolone, (iii) pyrazolone, (iv) thiobarbituric acid and (v) rhodanine as the variable acidic component are described. The deviations in their absorption maxima have been calculated and with the help of the deviation data, the relative acidities of the various acidic nuclei used have been determined.

Sensitising properties of some of the above merocyanines have also been evaluated.

In the present investigation, a number of dimethin and tetramethin merocyanines derived from 3-methyl benzo(f)quinoline as the fixed basic nucleus and one of the following (i) oxazolone, (ii) thiazolone, (iii) pyrazolone, (iv) thiobarbituric acid, (v) rhodanine as the variable acidic nucleus are described. Their absorption maxima have been determined and with the help of these data the deviations of the individual merocyanines have been calculated; the deviations are considered as the difference between absorption maxima of the dye concerned and the mean value of the absorption maxima of the corresponding symmetrical cyanine and the oxonol. Deviation is calculated as follows by considering the case of the dimethin merocyanine (I) derived from 3-methyl benzo(f)quinoline and the acidic nucleus 2-phenyl oxazolone. The absorption maximum of the trimethin symmetrical cyanine derived from 3-methyl benzo(f)quinoline (II) is $630\text{ m}\mu$ and that of the monomethin oxonol (III) derived from 2-phenyl oxazolone is $490\text{ m}\mu$. The dimethin merocyanine (I) composed of both the nuclei, however, absorbs at $559\text{ m}\mu$. The deviation is, therefore, $(560-559)\text{ m}\mu = 1\text{ m}\mu$.

It is now well established^{1,2} that this deviation can be used as a measure of relative acidity of different acidic nuclei linked to one fixed basic nucleus through a chromophoric chain in a series of merocyanines. The greater the deviation, the lower the acidity. Thus, deviation can be used as a measure of assessing the relative order of acidity of a series of acidic nuclei.

The data given in Table-I provide experimental verification of this relationship. It will be seen that in a series of merocyanines derived from 3-methyl benzo(f)quinoline as the fixed basic nucleus and a number of different acidic nuclei like oxazolone, thiazolone, pyrazolone, thiobarbituric acid and rhodanine, the respective deviations are 1, 3, 3.5, 25 and $40\text{ m}\mu$. The deviation for oxazolone is the lowest; the value being $1\text{ m}\mu$. The value for

1. L. G. S. Brooker, G. H. Keyes, R. H. Sprague, R. H. Vandyke, E. Vanlarke, G. Vanzandt and F. L. White, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5345.
2. L. G. S. Brooker, A. L. Sklar, H. W. J. Gussman, G. H. Keyes, A. L. Smith, R. H. Sprague, E. Van Lare, G. Van Zandt, F. L. White and W. W. Williams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 875.

deviation increases as we proceed from oxazolone to rhodanine. The deviation values indicate that the relative acidities of the five acidic nuclei lie in the order : oxazolone > thiazolone > pyrazolone > thiobarbituric acid > rhodanine.

Similarly in the case of tetramethin merocyanines, the deviation in case of the dye possessing the oxazolone nucleus is the lowest, the value being $2\text{ m}\mu$ (Table-II). The increase in the value of deviation follows the same sequence as above and therefore, the relative acidities of the five acidic nuclei conforms to the same order.

These experimental findings are in excellent agreement with previous findings and are also consistent with the results obtained by the application of the resonance concept.

TABLE I

Deviation data of dimethin merocyanines derived from benzo (f) quinoline and variable acidic nuclei

Nature of variable acidic nuclei	Absorption maxima in $\text{m}\mu$			Calc. λ_{max} in $\text{m}\mu$	Deviation in $\text{m}\mu$
	Sym. methin oxonol	Sym. trimethin cyanines	Dimethin merocy- anine		
2-phenyl oxazolone	490	630	559	560	1.0
2-Benzylthiothiazolone	520	630	572	575	3.0
2-Phenyl 3-methyl-pyrazolone	443	630	533	536.5	3.5
1,3-Diphenyl thiobarbituric acid	460	630	520	545	25.0
N-Phenyl rhodanine	522	630	536	576	40.0

TABLE II

Deviation data of tetramethin merocyanines derived from benzo (f) quinoline and variable acidic nuclei

Nature of variable acidic nuclei	Absorption maxima in $\text{m}\mu$			Calc. λ_{max} in $\text{m}\mu$	Deviation in $\text{m}\mu$
	Sym. trimethin oxonol	Sym. pentamethin cyanine	Tetramethin merocy- anine		
Oxazolone (2-phenyl)	590	730	658	660	2.0
2-Benzylthiothiazolone	620	730	672	675	3.0
1-Phenyl 3-methyl-pyrazolone	535	730	629	632.5	3.5
1,3, Diphenyl thiobarbituric acid	540	730	612	635	23.0
N-Phenyl rhodanine	620	730	630	675	45.0

The sensitisation spectra of some of the dyes have also been determined by the method of Doja³ with slight modification.

The light source was a 100 watt tungsten lamp instead of a 100 CP (point-o-lite) lamp. An wedge was placed in front of the slit to serve the purpose of rotating logarithmic sector used by Doja and coworkers. An initial scale was used to read the wave length by taking the standard lines of mercury, cadmium and potassium. To record the sensitisation spectra AGFA bromide papers were used.

It will be seen from the following Table-III that the sensitisation range and sensitisation maxima roughly correspond to absorption maxima. All the dyes studied are good sensitisers in their respective ranges. The sensitivity of AGFA bromide papers lies between 400-490 $m\mu$.

TABLE III

Sensitisation data of merocyanines derived from benzo(f)quinoline as the fixed basic nucleus and other variable acidic nuclei

Variable acidic nucleus	Nature of the dye	Absorption maximum in $m\mu$	Sensitisation in $m\mu$	
			range	maximum
Pyrazolone	dimethin	533	500-560	555
-do-	tetramethin	629	500-620	580
Oxazolone	dimethin	559	500-590	550
-do-	tetramethin	658	580-640	620

The preparation of the dyes are described in the Experimental.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Methyl benzo(f)quinoline was obtained by the interaction of beta-naphthylamine, paraldehyde, and hydrochloric acid following the procedure of Doebner and Miller⁴.

By heating the above quinoline in a sealed tube at 100° with methyl iodide, the methiodide was obtained which was recrystallised from absolute ethanol. m.p. 243-245° (decomp), yield—90% (Found : I, 37.92, formula requires I, 38.09%).

⁴. Doebner Von Miller, *Ber*, 1884, 17, 1711.

Dimethin merocyanines derived from 3-methyl benzo(f)quinoline

4-[(4-Methyl benzo(f)quinolyl 3-ylidene) ethylidene]1-phenyl-3-methyl pyrazolone: 3-Methyl benzo(f)quinoline methiodide (0.67 g.) and 4-(acetanilido methylene)-1-phenyl-3-methyl pyrazolone (0.56 g) were dissolved in minimum amount of absolute alcohol and triethylamine (0.2 g.) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 minutes. The excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The gummy substance which separated was washed with water and recrystallised from pyridine water.

Other dimethin merocyanines were prepared similarly from the intermediates of other ketomethylene compounds. The analytical data etc., of the above compound as well as other dimethin merocyanines are described in Table-IV.

TABLE IV

Dimethin merocyanines derived from benzo(f)quinoline as the fixed basic nucleus and other variable acidic nuclei

Nature of variable acidic nuclei	M.P. °C	Yield %	Abs. max. in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
2-Phenyl oxazolone	250	57	559	78.68	79.36	4.63	4.76
2-Benzylthiothiazolone	250	43	572	70.69	70.91	4.51	4.54
1-Phenyl 3-methyl pyrazolone	164	53	533	79.01	79.80	5.07	5.37
1,3-Diphenyl thiobarbituric acid	201(d)	45	520	74.36	74.85	4.39	4.48
3-Phenyl rhodanine	74(d)	48	536	75.87	76.14	4.32	4.57

Tetramethin merocyanines derived from 3-methyl benzo(f)quinoline: The general method followed for the preparation of tetramethin merocyanines is described below.

3-methyl benzo(f) quinoline methiodide (1 mole) and acetanilido allylidene derivative of the desired ketomethylene compounds (1 mole) were dissolved in minimum quantity of absolute alcohol. After addition of a few drops of triethylamine, the reaction mixture was refluxed in a water bath for 5-10 min. In most cases removal of solvent caused deposition of a gummy matter which solidified by washing with water. The dye was recrystallised from ethanol.

The analytical data etc., of various tetramethin merocyanines derived from benzo(f) quinoline are described in Table-V.

TABLE V

Tetramethin merocyanines derived from benzo(f) quinoline as the fixed basic nucleus and other variable acidic nuclei

Nature of variable acidic nuclei	M.P. °C	Yield %	Abs. max. in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
2-Phenyl oxazolone	162	45	658	80.05	80.19	4.83	4.95
2-Benzylthiothiazolone	155	53	672	72.00	72.10	4.89	4.93
1-Phenyl-3-methyl-pyrazolone	250	65	629	80.18	80.58	5.49	5.51
1,3-Diphenyl thiobarbituric acid	250	35	612	75.03	75.69	4.56	4.64
3-Phenyl rhodanine	187	44	630	76.85	77.14	4.69	4.76

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